

NARENDRA MODI

Prime Minister of India

सत्यमेव जयते

Welcome : Sardar Dilbag Singh Khalsa

- [User Dashboard](#)
- [Appeal Dashboard](#)
- [Lodge Public Grievance](#)
- [Account Activity](#)
- [Edit Profile](#)
- [Change Password](#)
- [Sign out](#)

Grievance Details

Registration Number

PMOPG/E/2023/0169969

Name

Sardar Dilbag Singh Khalsa

Date of receipt

26/08/2023

Address

Mehtanagar Pandit deendayal upadhyay ward mehtanagar
Pandit deendayal upadhyay ward mehtanagar

State

Chhattisgarh

District

Balodabazar-Bhatapara

Mobile Number

9981240811

Email ID

sdskdilbag1994@gmail.com

Phone Number

Not Provided

Grievance Description

Railways, (Railway Board) >> Miscellaneous

Railway Board/ Zone/ PSU/ PU/ Office : South East Central Railway - Bilaspur

Dear Sir

I am Sardar Dilbag Singh Khalsa , PhD student at IIT Bhubaneswar. I am travelling by train for last 10 years. When we purchase a ticket of sleeper class , some times, tickets are not confirm and we get RAC ticket. If we are travelling 16-48 hours it's very tough to sustain in a single seat. We can't even sleep. In case of General ticket, the conditions are worse! We don't even get place to seat. Providing facilities to the Public is government responsibility. Then why this system has no growth for over decades. It's not only about South East Central Railways. This is the problem of every Railway Jones. I have request from our Hournable Prime Minister to bring some changes regarding this issue. We can add extra coaches to avoid RAC ticket , and can also add more general coaches , so that people from poor background can avail good facility. We have reached to moon it's sign that we are progressing, but we also have to solve the real ground level problem of

our society.

Thanks & Regards
Sardar Dilbag Singh Khalsa
PhD Physics Scholar SBS
IIT Bhubaneswar

Communication Details

Sn.	Date of Action	Action	From	To
1	26/08/2023	RECEIVED THE GRIEVANCE	You	Prime Minister's Office
2	11/09/2023	CASE DISPOSED OF	DRM Bilaspur	You

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